

D7.1: Press release

[WP7 – Communication and dissemination]

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Abstract

This report describes the process of drafting and reviewing the SIENNA press release was issued on October 19, 2017 by the University of Twente. All SIENNA partners were invited to review the press release and encouraged to translate and disseminate versions of the text tailored to the communication needs of the respective partner organisation.

Document history

Version	Date	Description	Reason for change	Distribution
V0.1	30 Oct 2017	First Draft		Main contributors
V0.1	31 Oct 2017	Final version		

Information in this report that may influence other SIENNA tasks

Linked task	Points of relevance
D7.3 Communication and dissemination plan	This report describes process for SIENNA launch press-release. Procedures for tracking will be developed in D7.3 deliverable report.

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1. Introduction

To prepare for the project launch, a website for the SIENNA project was developed and launched on September 29, 2017 (Friday) in order to be up and running for its official start date on October 1 (Sunday). The site was delivered ahead of time to ensure the project had a point of contact when the press-release (D7.1) was launched on October 19, 2017.

The University of Twente had already issued a press release in Dutch on April 28, 2017 after signing of the signing of the Grant Agreement ([Onderzoek naar ethische en juridische aspecten van nieuwe technologie](#)) which was mirrored in English on the University of Twente website ([Research on ethical and legal aspects of new technologies](#)). The Dutch release received some media attention in the Netherlands and it is expected that this will take away some of the local interest in the October 19 press release.

2. Drafting and reviewing release text

WP7 (Communication and dissemination) drafted a global press release in English to be sent through the press office at the University of Twente. All partners were offered a week to review the text. The text was re-worked based on comments from the coordinator, work package leaders, the University of Twente's press office and Trilateral Research's communications and marketing manager. The final version was agreed with the coordinator and deputy coordinator, and then sent to all partners one week before its launch.

3. Encouraging local releases

All partners were sent the press release text one week in advance of launch (October 2, 2017) and were informed that the English text was intended as a global press release, sent through the University of Twente press office using AlphaGalileo at 10 AM on October 19, 2017. Partners were informed that the text was under embargo until then and that they should not release any English language versions through AlphaGalileo.

Partners were encouraged to translate and disseminate local releases in the form of web news, or translated press releases. They were advised to consider the English text as building blocks for their own stories and were encouraged to translate the message to showcase their areas of expertise and contribution to the project. The version sent to partners included suggestions (highlighted in blue) to show where and how the text could be tailored to fit partner's own communication channels.

Partners were encouraged to report to the WP7 leader whether they intended to use the text and offered help with any local English versions. Partners were also encouraged to post links to the SIENNA website from their own web, social media and in other channels at any time.

4. Embargo

Before the review process begun, partners were informed that the text was under embargo until 12:00, October 19, 2017. They were advised that the embargo means they should wait to publish their version of the text until after the Twente release has been sent, and that they were free to use it at any time from then on, to ensure any local communications fit with the needs of the respective organisations.

5. Official and local releases

The official version of the release was sent through AlphaGalileo and published on the University of Twente website at 10:00 on October 19, 2017. The text was mirrored on the SIENNA website at 10:10. Trilateral Research issued a version of the text as web news at 11:12, and Uppsala University's Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics followed at 12:00, simultaneously publishing a Swedish version of the text. The University of Granada published their version of the text on October 26, 2017. The Dalian University of Technology and Federal University of Rio de Janeiro have also planned releases.

A version of the content was published on the Ethics Blog (www.ethicsblog.crb.uu.se) and the Swedish sister blog (www.etikbloggen.uu.se) on October 31, 2017. The Spanish version of the release was also shared on Twitter using the hashtag #SiennaEthics on October 26, 2017 by the University of Granada (@CanalUGR) and Javier Vallis Prieto (@javi_valls). Tracking of local releases and media interest will continue during the autumn of 2017.

Figure 1: #SiennaEthics on Twitter

6. Official and local versions: links

SIENNA official press releases

- [Preparing the ground for responsible innovation, University of Twente](#), University of Twente, October 19, 2017
- [Onderzoek naar ethische en juridische aspecten van nieuwe technologie](#), University of Twente, April 28, 2017

English versions

- [SIENNA: Preparing the ground for responsible innovation](#), SIENNA website: www.sienna-project.eu, October 19, 2017
- [SIENNA: Preparing the ground for responsible innovation](#), Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics (CRB), October 19, 2017
- [Trilateral to support the co-ordination of multi-million Euro project on ethics and human rights impact of new technologies](#), Trilateral research web news, October 19, 2017

Spanish

- [Un equipo de investigación internacional evaluará el impacto de las nuevas tecnologías en los derechos humanos](#), canal UGR, University of Granada, October 26, 2017

Swedish

- [SIENNA-projektet lägger grunden för ansvarsfull teknikanvändning](#), News from the Centre for Research Ethics & Bioethics (CRB), Uppsala University, October 19, 2017

Press coverage in Dutch

- [Dit zijn de 3 ethische grenzen aan technologie, vindt UT-professor](#), Tubantia May 13, 2017
- [Groot Europees onderzoek naar regels voor nieuwe technologieën](#), NPO Radio 1, May 2, 2017

Annex 1: Release text

The following text with suggestions to adapt content was sent to all partners one week before the release was issued:

Edit the title so that it fits with your channels: this works for Twente.

International research team to assess ethical and human rights impact of new technologies

Preparing the ground for responsible innovation

Policy makers all over the world struggle to assess the ethical and human rights impact of new research in genetics and genomics, human enhancement, artificial intelligence and robotics. Researchers from four continents have teamed up in the SIENNA project to help improve existing ethical and legal frameworks. The project receives a financial contribution of just under €4 million from the EU's Horizon 2020 programme. Make sure to mention your organisation's role in the introduction.

It is difficult to predict the consequences of developing and using new technologies. We interact with robots, smart devices, intelligent software, prosthetics and implants in daily life. At the same time, new and improved technologies for genetic and genomic research are making their way from research to patients and consumers in the form of cheaper and more accessible tests and screening. **Suggestion: Adapt by adding an example that is specific to your contribution.**

Today, we are closer to scenarios we could only have pictured in science fiction a few decades ago. Genetic diagnosis is not new. These tools have been used for decades to screen and test individuals and families with hereditary disorders. However, new gene editing tools that could help treat genetic diseases are on the horizon. At least in theory, this could be used to 'design' or modify specific genetic traits in humans. Similarly, education and exercise have long been understood as tools to enhance our abilities. Newly developed technologies promise a more specific and more effective way to enhancement. Advances in artificial intelligence and robotics could perhaps promise to fill jobs currently done by humans. Which, in turn, could affect what employers expect from their staff.

Who is accountable for the different uses that we make of new powerful research and technology? What kind of regulations should be in place and what concerns should they address? The SIENNA project sets the ground for ethical codes and recommendations to improve existing legal frameworks, bringing together researchers from Europe, Asia, Africa and America. **Suggestion: Adapt by adding text about your organisation and work.**

"The SIENNA project will examine the practical and ethical questions of what can and should be permitted in research and technological development. Our proposals will be based on ethical assessments that build on extensive consultations with international stakeholders and leading

experts in genomics, human enhancement, AI & robotics. Together with surveys of public opinion and citizen panels, this will ensure outcomes that are relevant, well-supported and more likely to be implemented”, says Rowena Rodrigues, Senior Research Analyst at Trilateral Research and deputy coordinator of SIENNA.

Suggestion: Complement (or swap) quotes from Rowena and Philip with one from your PI, explaining what you bring to the project:

The project also raises challenging philosophical questions. Where do we draw the line between health and illness? Cosmetic surgery for a burn victim is different from the same procedure for someone suffering from mild social distress. One is a treatment, one is considered enhancement. What do we expect from intelligent software in terms of morality? Are we willing to give up privacy to have our genome screened for genetic disorders, or our personal liberty to interact with machines?

Both the public and policy makers are concerned about these issues. In recent years, there have been numerous academic publications on the ethical and human rights issues of new and emerging technologies in genomics, enhancement and robotics. SIENNA takes a new and extended approach by looking at these areas together.

“SIENNA is the first project to undertake an extensive, international study of present and future ethical and human rights implications of genomics, enhancement and robotics, and how people feel about their use. We are also one of the first projects to work closely with organisations in science, industry and policy to refine policies and ethics codes for better development and use of the innovations from these fields”, says Philip Brey, Professor of Philosophy of Technology, University of Twente, and coordinator of SIENNA.

Contact and more information

Suggestion: Adapt by adding (or replacing with) local contact information

More information on the SIENNA website: www.sienna-project.eu

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About SIENNA

The SIENNA project - *Stakeholder-informed ethics for new technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impact* - has received just under € 4 million for a 3,5 year project under the European Union's [H2020 research and innovation programme](#), grant agreement No 741716.

The project is coordinated from the University of Twente in the Netherlands with support from Trilateral Research Ltd, United Kingdom. Other partners include Uppsala University (Sweden), Helsinki Foundation for Human Rights (Poland), the European Network of Research Ethics Committees, University of Granada (Spain), Ionian University (Greece), Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (Brazil), Dalian University of Technology (China), French National Centre for Scientific Research (Sciences Po) (France), and the University of Cape Town (South Africa). SIENNA has two associate partners, Chuo University (Japan) and the Berkman Klein Center for Internet & Society (USA). The project is also supported by organisations such as the World Health Organization, the

Human Genome Organisation, IEEE, ACM, EURobotics, ALLEA (All European Academies), UNESCO and the Council of Europe.

Disclaimer: This text and its contents reflects only SIENNA's view. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Suggestion: Add a short “about” for your own organisation